

SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF THE DAILY LIFESTYLE OF WOMEN OF TASHKENT OASIS DURING WORLD WAR II

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***Abstract.** This article provides detailed information about the socio-economic aspects of the daily life and courage of women of Tashkent oasis during World War II.*

***Keywords:** orders "Red Star" and "For the Fatherland", State Defense Committee (SDC), Red Army, the medal "For Courage".*

INTRODUCTION

If we look at the history of mankind, we can see how many events it has experienced as a direct participant. In the 20th century, mankind achieved great successes in the development of science and technology, in the field of inventions and discoveries. In particular, the Second World War brought suffering, losses and destruction on an unprecedented scale in the history of mankind. This war was waged by the major powers of the world with the aim of dividing the world economically, politically, territorially and strategically. As the initiator of this war of extermination, Nazi Germany began it, considering itself sufficiently prepared for war conditions. Since the main battles were fought on the territory of Hitler's Germany and the Soviet state, Uzbekistan was also able to demonstrate its worthy courage by participating in this war as part of the alliance.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

As the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, noted, "No matter how we look at the Second World War, no matter under what ideology and under whose leadership this war was fought, we will always remember those who died on the battlefields for the bright future of our Motherland, the people, and the clear sky, and those who lost their lives untimely. This is bitter, but no one has the right to forget this supreme truth, and we will not allow it." The war years are an integral part of the history of Uzbekistan. We will not remove a single page from our history. This history is ours, no one has the right to forget it. The Uzbek population was voluntarily drawn into the war, took up arms and fought against the fascist invaders with all their strength and determination. Along with the brave men, brave women who fought for the prosperity of the country, who were selfless and heroic, also fought. During World War II, Uzbek women showed heroism, demonstrating their patriotism, humanity, and selflessness. As the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, said: "In the entire enlightened world, there is a special issue called the interests of women and girls, and it is not for nothing that great importance is attached to studying it and finding a solution. I think that there is no need to talk about the future of such a society if women are not given sufficient attention." In this regard, it is important to carefully study the experience of the recent Soviet era and draw the necessary lessons from it. The Soviet state also fought against fascism's domination of the world, under the idea that it was fighting to prevent the catastrophes that it could bring to humanity. In fact, both ruling powers fought for world domination. On June 30, 1941, the State Defense Committee (SDC) was formed under the leadership of I.V. Stalin, and all affairs were concentrated in the hands of a single person. He knew well that the fight against Nazi Germany, which was armed to the teeth, would not be

easy. In order to adapt the Soviet state to the conditions of war, on July 3, 1941, Stalin was forced to address the people on the radio and tell the whole truth. After this incident, demonstrations were held in all the states, regions, districts and rural districts of the Soviet state, and appeals were made to the people, calling on them to prepare the population for war conditions, to strengthen their sense of courage and patriotism in the fight against the invaders, and to defend their homeland with all their might and determination, and to hate the fascists, calling on their people and everyone to join this honorable cause. According to the resolution of the State Defense Committee of September 18, 1941 “On the compulsory transfer of military service to citizens of the USSR”, “every citizen of the Soviet Union capable of bearing arms must be ready to take up arms and defend his Motherland”. In response, all the brave boys of the Union, including 50,365 brave Uzbeks from Surkhan oasis, took up arms in life-and-death battles and fought mercilessly against the enemy. In the early years of the war, the Soviet authorities implemented their strict demands, a policy of violence, and decisive and drastic measures to subordinate them to the center. In fact, he used ordinary people's representatives with his Stalinist policies to defeat the enemy in any way he could. Although they knew that this was unfair. Despite this, the representatives of the Soviet state did not back down from anything in the path of their lofty goals. We know from history that on June 22, 1941, military mobilization was announced, and in the first years, 32 thousand of the sons of Uzbekistan, who had a fire in their hearts, as part of the Soviet Union, applied to go to the front. On June 23-24, demonstrations were held in Bukhara, Andijan, Namangan, Fergana and other cities. On June 23, a demonstration was also held in Nukus, Karakalpakstan, and many residents volunteered to fight against the fascists. At the beginning of the war, Uzbek women took turns in field work for their fathers, brothers and husbands who had gone to war, including driving tractors and picking cotton, and generally performed not only heavy work, but also work that was not considered appropriate for women. By October 15, 1941, 800 women had come out with the call to “take the place of the young men who had gone to the front.” The number of brave women who could take up arms in the fight against the invaders without being busy with field work, housework, and raising children increased, and now they, considering it a matter of honor to fight alongside brave boys on the war fronts against the fascists, went to war, as well. On July 5, 1941, a rally was held in the Oktabr district of Tashkent, in which 15,000 women participated. At this rally, the slogan "Dear sisters! Let us all stand together and defend our beloved Motherland, let us work on machines, transport, tractors and combines to replace our husbands and brothers. No one has the right to sit idly by in this war. We will win behind the front lines." Workers, intellectuals, civil servants, artists and singers, medical workers and young students, as well as any people with fire in their hearts, were mobilized for World War II. They fought with all their might not to give their beloved homeland to the enemy. In the early years of the war, 100,000 young men and women from Tashkent were mobilized to the front. There were also volunteers from other regions. In particular, 1,316 people from Samarkand region applied to be sent to the front, and by August 4, 1941, their number had reached 2,988. 613 of them were women. However, in each region there were many brave and courageous women who, full of anger and rage, went to war in the fight against the invaders. Indeed, nurses, theater and art workers, female students and their comrades-in-arms, as well as brave women with a strong love for the Motherland, went to the fronts of World War II. However, almost all of them went to war as volunteers. From the city of Shakhrisabz alone, 1,148 people volunteered for the army in the first few days of the war, 10 of whom were women. Due to the intensification of local efforts to prepare the population for war conditions and to carry

out propaganda against the fascist invaders, the ranks of women who went to fight expanded. In particular, the Soviet Union sent 37,000 young men and women from Tashkent region to the Red Army during 1941-1943. Of these, 10,000 were accepted into the National units. In the fight against the fascist invaders, 15,252 men and women from Syrdarya region went to the life-and-death battles. 200,000 men and women from Tashkent region were mobilized for World War II. In response to military mobilization, 1,156 applications (147 of them were women) were received from Khorezm region to the military commissariat within a few days of the start of the war. 1,213 women from the region learned new production professions and began to show their activity in place of those who went to war. In the terrible battles against fascism, more than 67,300 Khorezmians took part in this bloody struggle, risking their lives. One of the women who went to fight to defend their beloved homeland, which was part of the Soviet Union, was Roza Ibrahimova. In the summer of 1943, after graduating from a communications school in Uzbekistan, she went to work at a radio station near Moscow. Roza Ibrahimova showed worthy heroism by participating in the battles for the capture of Berlin. In the first week of the war, 1,735 applications (423 of which were women) were received from Fergana residents asking them to mobilize for the war. 8 sanitary detachments were formed in Fergana (280 women trained in them) and 6 sanitary detachments - in Kokand (220 women trained in them). During the war years, several hundred thousand volunteers from Fergana took part in the fight against fascism. Propaganda and agitation work was carried out in the localities on the fight against the fascist invaders. The hatred and anger of the population within the Soviet Union against the enemy increased. Including Andijan, a total of 97 thousand people were mobilized for the war. A certain part of them were women. The Soviet Union quickly developed various decrees to combat the enemy. According to the decree of September 18, 1941, it was necessary to "introduce military weapons to everyone who is able to hold a weapon and prepare them for war conditions." In this process, women also got acquainted with weapons, learned military methods, and decided to fight for the defense of the country. All women in the Soviet Union: Turkmen, Kazakh, Azerbaijani, Tajik, Kyrgyz, and also Uzbek women showed heroism. In the winter of 1941, the German army attacked Ukraine and other regions. A more powerful mobilization took place on the territory of the Soviet state, in which Uzbek women, like women of other nations, also participated. Their heroism was recognized. In particular, Lieutenant Colonel Savvin wrote that a Komsomol girl named Rakhima Alimova from Bukhara was especially heroic in the battles for Ukraine.

From July 18 to July 28, 1943, dozens of battles took place on the banks of the Northern Don River for the Donbas. At that time, 97 wounded soldiers and officers were provided with emergency medical care under machine gun and mortar fire. During the 20-day offensive battles that lasted from September 1 to September 21, Rakhima Alimova performed a heroic act. This time, 30 soldiers and officers were taken out of the battlefield with their weapons and provided with the necessary medical care. The surviving soldiers and officers still express their gratitude to Rakhima Alimova. Jamila Husaynova, one of these women, after military training, entered the battle on the banks of the Northern Don River, and then participated in the liberation of Ukraine on the southwestern front line.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Soviet government quickly intensified the training of doctors and nurses for war conditions. In particular, in October 1941, the call "Prepare for Sanitary Defense" was well received by the people, and in places they practiced blood transfusion operations, military field

operations, including the work of nurses and surgeons, preparing for the front. Training courses were organized in the places to train medical personnel. In particular, Tashkent and Samarkand Medical Institutes trained 3,257 doctors from 1941 to 1945, and 4,864 medical personnel were also trained. However, 266 nurses were trained in 25 sanitary brigades. After graduating from such educational institutions, they went to the front and provided medical care to wounded soldiers and officers. Our savior women, such as senior lieutenants Sobira Majidova and Maryam Yusupova, risked their lives to take wounded soldiers and officers out of the fire of war. That is why dozens of soldiers like Sohibbayev, Zuev and Mamatov will never forget their sisters who saved their lives. In the harsh winter of 1942, Sobira Majidova skillfully applied ointment to the wounds of wounded soldiers in cellars not far from Lake Ilmen, and walked through swamps alongside soldiers on the banks of Desna River and in the forests of Branyansk, demonstrating her fighting spirit. Along with Muqaddam Ashrapova, who graduated from the medical faculty of the institute in 1941, her friends Anvara Muharramova, Polatoy Kadirova, and Sobira Majidova also went to war and showed selflessness to save the soldiers. Rahmat Hamroyeva, along with her friends Qumri and Saida, also went to the front to fight against the invaders, risking their lives. Rayhon Hamroyeva and her companions provided medical care to the soldiers. In January 1943, a group of doctors joined the troops stationed on the Volga. Among these doctors was Ruqiya Ismailova from Uzbekistan, who also provided worthy assistance to wounded soldiers on the battlefields. On the fronts of World War II, Uzbek women were able to demonstrate the courage and heroism characteristic of an Uzbek girl in saving the precious lives of soldiers and officers of the Allied forces. Such brave women not only demonstrated their worthy heroism as nurses, but also in the fight against the enemy.

In June 1942, 21 girls from Bukhara applied to go to war for the liberation of the Motherland. 11 of them were girls from Uzbekistan. One of these women was Khosiyat Halimova, who graduated from the Institute of Signals, served in the 90th Rifle Brigade, and showed heroism in connecting broken communication wires and restoring communication on the battlefields. Roza Ibrohimova, who volunteered to go to war, showed heroism in the summer of 1943 by going to a radio station near Moscow and participating in the war as a scout. Zebo Ganieva risked her life as a scout and gained fame by participating in the "Til" operation 12 times (capturing a live prisoner in order to learn about the enemy's plans). Zebo Ganiyeva, in accordance with I.V. Stalin's decree No. N-227 of July 28, 1942, "Not a single step back," crushed 28 fascists to death. During the war years, Hanifa Mamatkazina, along with the 132nd artillery unit on the 2nd Ukrainian Front, saved the lives of hundreds of soldiers and showed heroism in the battles for Czechoslovakia, Austria, the Carpathians and Romania, while liberating the cities of Kharkov, Prague and Budapest. In general, women, wherever they were and in whatever circumstances, considered the homeland a matter of honor and fought against the enemy with weapons in their hands. During the war years, the issue of the human spirit was a key factor. In order to inspire our soldiers and officers in the fight against the enemy, various concert groups organized tours, providing Soviet fighters with morale in the fight against the fascists. Indeed, the performance of Uzbek Philharmonic under the leadership of Tamara Khanum, who received the title of People's Artist of the USSR and the USSR State Prize, was very popular with the fighters. In particular, Tamarakhanim in her memoirs - "We would hide in shelters, wait for the German air raids to end, and then continue the concert. During the concert, the fighters would not disperse until they were called out by name or by the entire unit. We knew neither fear nor fatigue, as the concert gave the audience great strength and spirit."

Tamarakhanim gave 1,000 concerts for the fighters during the war, inspiring them to victory. She performed a Karakalpak folk song on the stage of the Red Army Officers' House in Vienna. One of the heroic women who inspired the fighting spirit of the soldiers and officers of the Soviet Union was Rahima Alimova. Rahima Alimova, along with drama theater artist E'tibor Oripova, participated in the battles on the outskirts of Moscow, Stalingrad, Kursk and Minsk during the war years, demonstrating their creative abilities and inspiring the soldiers to victory. In order to inspire the soldiers tired of the war, the artists of our republic, led by Gavhar Rakhimova, performed cultural services in the hottest areas of the front and helped the soldiers defeat the enemy with their beautiful songs. The courage shown by women, who fought alongside Uzbek soldiers and officers on the fronts of World War II, among all the war participants in the Soviet Union, and who risked their lives to defend their homeland, ensuring its freedom, destiny, and independence, is commendable. They were encouraged by the leaders of the Soviet Union to inspire them to fight the enemy. Zebo Ganiyeva was awarded the Order of the Red Banner for her courage. Such women made up the majority. Hanifa Mamatkazina was also awarded the Order of the Red Banner twice, the Order of Glory of the III degree, and the Medal "For Courage" twice for her services to the Motherland. Soliha Davronova participated in the battle for the city of Zaporozhye in the summer of 1943. For her heroism in battle, she was awarded the medal "For Courage". The Motherland rewarded Soliha Davronova's labors, placing on her breast the orders "Red Star" and "For the Fatherland" of the 2nd degree. Rakhima Alimova was awarded the medal "For Courage" for her heroism. Together with a group of scouts, she went behind the enemy's back and set an example for everyone by destroying the Germans. For this heroism, Rakhima Alimova was awarded the Order of the Red Banner. Rayhon Hamroyeva saved many soldiers from death in the battles near Gomel. She was awarded the medal "For Courage" for her courage in battle. For her courage in battle, Khosiyat Halimova was awarded the medal "For Courage" and "For Combat Merit" and other medals. Jamila Husainova was awarded combat medals for her courage in war.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth saying that the Second World War was aimed at protecting humanity and society in general from the scourge of fascism. Representatives of all nationalities, fighters, soldiers, officers and women of the Soviet Union, including Uzbek women, participated in this war. Since such women had strong feelings of patriotism and humanity, the fact that they considered the defense of the Motherland a matter of honor and responsibility and went to the war fronts is a great feat in itself. The brave women of the Soviet state, and in particular Uzbeks, demonstrated their heroism and courage in the fight against the fascist invaders. As with any event, there is a beginning and an end. The Second World War ended with the surrender of Japan on September 2, 1945. It ended with the victory over fascism. At the forefront of any event is a person and his interests and needs. The heads of state who wanted this war to end in victory did not give up any work to dominate the world, but fought for only one goal, namely, to win the war. Almost all the soldiers and officers of the Soviet Union who went to fight in the early years of World War II died on the battlefields. Despite this, people went to the war fronts. If we pay attention, the fighters who went to war after 1943 returned. However, many of them were wounded and disabled. Thousands of them volunteered for the front, and although many of those who initially went to war died, thousands of people went to war to compensate them, considering the defense of the Motherland honorable. The people of the Soviet Union, including Uzbeks, had a strong fighting spirit, and were always ready to fight against the enemy in order to honorably justify the trust of

their people and their parents. The people of the countries of the Soviet Union, despite being defeated in the early years of the war, did not retreat and only moved forward for their freedom. Because these people had a strong sense of honor and fighting spirit. The role of Uzbek women in ending this war with victory is incomparable. Many of these women fought on the terrible battlefields from the beginning of the war, despite the roar of cannons, the rain of arrows, and the scream of mines, with the courage and fighting spirit characteristic of their Uzbek women. Uzbek women, like other women, not only fought against the fascists, but despite the hail of bullets and flames, they also applied ointment to the wounds of brave and courageous soldiers and officers who had sacrificed their lives for the homeland, performed complex surgeries, and helped them return to the battlefield. Such kind of women healed the brave warriors and gave them the fighting spirit to return to the battlefield. Indeed, on the war fronts, they demonstrated their ability to defend their homeland with the heroism and courage typical of Uzbek women, holding weapons in their hands and defending their beloved land in a bloody war, not to give it to a strong and insidious enemy.

REFERENCES

1. Karimov I. A. Vatan sajdagoh kabi muqaddasdir. - T.: O'zbekiston. 1996. T.3. - B.81.
2. Karimov I. A. O'zbekiston: Milliy istiqlol, iqtisod, siyosat, mafkura. I jild.- T.: O'zbekiston, 1996. - B. 54.
3. Inoyatov H. G'alabaga qo'shilgan hissa. - T. Fan, 1975.
4. O'zbekiston tarixi (1917-1991) 2-kitob. -T.:O'zbekiston, 2019.
5. Surxondaryo tarixi Tursunov S, Qobilov E, Murtazoev B, Pardayev T. - T.: Sharq, 2004.
6. Xotira Toshkent shahri. 1- kitob. - T.: Qomuslar bosh tahririyati. -B.6.
7. Xotira Samarqand shahri.1- kitob. - T.: Ibn Sino nomidagi matbaa- nashriyoti birlashmasi, 1994.
8. Yorbozorova Z. Ikkinchi jahon urushida o'zbekistonlik xotin- qizlarning faoliyati. B.M.I.Qarshi. 2013.
9. Xotira Xorazm shahri.1- kitob. - T.: G'afur G'ulom nomidagi adabiyot. 1994. 10. Xotira Farg'ona shahri. 2- kitob. - T.: Qomuslar bosh tahririyati.1994.
10. Xotira Andijon. 1- kitob. - T.: Mehnat. 1994.
11. Adham Rahmat. Shinelli qizLar. - T.: , 1970.
12. Jo'rayev T. O'zbekiston jangchilari Ulug' Vatan urushi frontlarida. - T.: Fan, 1975. - B. 32.
13. Sirojev O. Fashizm ustidan erishilgan g'alabada Buxoroliklarning roli. - T.: O'zbekiston, 1996. -B. 337-338.
14. Vatan sharafi uchun. 1944-yil 16- yanvar. N-3. (193). Tuzuvchilar: Shamsutdinov R. To'plam. Ikkinchi jahon urushi fronti va gazetalari. II jild. -T.: Akademnashr, 2017. - B.26.
15. Qizil Armiya 1944-yil 7-mart. N- 20. (125). Tuzuvchi: Shamsutdinov R. To'plam. II jild. Ikkinchi jahon urushi va fronti gazetalari. - T.: Akademnashr, 2017. - B.441.